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Drag reduction of slender blunt-based bodies using optimized rear cavities

M. Lorite-Díez^a, J.I. Jiménez-González^{a,*}, C. Gutiérrez-Montes^a, C. Martínez-Bazán^a

^a*Departamento de Ingeniería Mecánica y Minera. Universidad de Jaén. Campus de las Lagunillas, 23071, Jaén, Spain.*

Abstract

We have investigated the use of the adjoint sensitivity formulation to design efficient passive control strategies aiming at reducing the drag coefficient of a slender blunt-based body with a straight rear cavity. In particular, two control techniques consisting in wake modifications generated by placing small control cylinders in the near wake and by geometry variations of the cavity respectively, have been evaluated numerically. Thus, we have computed the turbulent flow sensitivity of the drag coefficient to localized forcing for a two-dimensional body with a straight cavity at $Re = \rho U_\infty H / \mu = 2000$, where U_∞ is the free-stream velocity, ρ and μ the fluid density and viscosity respectively and H the body height, showing that the highest values of sensitivity are obtained near the cavity edges. The effect of placing a pair of control cylinders around the most sensitive locations has been studied, obtaining a largest drag reduction of only 0.6%. Alternatively, a most efficient control strategy based on shape optimization has been thoroughly investigated. The drag shape sensitivity on the body surface (Othmer, 2014), computed using the former linear adjoint formulation, has been used in combination with a free-form deformation algorithm (Han et al., 2011), to guide the local structure deformations of the cavity, providing progressive drag reductions until the optimal, curved, shape is achieved. To deeply analyze the physical mechanisms behind the drag reduction provided by the optimal cavity, we have also performed more realistic three-dimensional numerical simulations using an IDDES model at two different Reynolds numbers, $Re = 2000$ and 20000 . The results corroborate the sensitivity analysis, obtaining a total drag reduction of 25.6% at $Re = 2000$ and 43.9% at $Re = 20000$, with respect to the original body without cavity, and 21.7% at $Re = 2000$ and 29.6% at $Re = 20000$ with respect to the body with a straight cavity. These reductions are mainly achieved by the inwards deflection of the flow upon detachment and a flow deceleration at the trailing edge due to an adverse pressure gradient introduced by the curved shape of the optimal cavity walls. Both combined effects reduce the size of the recirculation bubble formed behind the body, increasing the base pressure, and consequently, decreasing the drag. Furthermore, the addition of the optimized base cavity reduces the amplitude of the velocity fluctuations behind the body and stabilizes the wake, which becomes less chaotic and more two-dimensional.

1. Introduction

The flow around heavy vehicles, such as trucks or buses, is highly three-dimensional, chaotic and turbulent. This flow is mainly characterized by a massive flow separation, which induces the development of a wake behind the body and the periodic shedding of vortices, resulting into the appearance of major fluctuating aerodynamic forces in the structure. These forces have a great impact on the vehicle stability and, more importantly, on the fuel consumption, the latter being governed by the drag force. In this regard, it is estimated that 20% of the whole energy in a heavy vehicle is devoted to overcome the aerodynamic losses (Choi et al., 2014). Thus, these kinds of flows have been extensively studied in the last decades (Ahmed et al., 1984; Han et al., 1996; Pastoor et al., 2008) with the aim at better understanding the present features and the governing physical mechanisms as well as to develop new, more efficient flow-control methods or to improve the existing ones in terms of drag reduction and flow induced loads.

*Corresponding author

Email addresses: mldiez@ujaen.es (M. Lorite-Díez), jignacio@ujaen.es (J.I. Jiménez-González), cgmontes@ujaen.es (C. Gutiérrez-Montes), cmbazan@ujaen.es (C. Martínez-Bazán)

Many of the aforementioned investigations considered simplified vehicle models (see e.g. Ahmed et al., 1984; Pastoor et al., 2008), to emulate the flow conditions around real heavy vehicles. As a result, a large amount of approaches and devices have been proposed, which can be grouped into active and passive flow control techniques, the latter being easier to implement. In general, these strategies aim at modifying the near wake, and can be implemented either by means of open (Parkin et al., 2014) or closed (Henning et al., 2007; Pastoor et al., 2008) flow control loops. For instance, regarding active flow control systems, sophisticated and complex devices have been studied, some of them being based on the use of actuators (Beaudoin et al., 2006), suction/blowing strategies (Sevilla and Martínez-Bazán, 2004; Sanmiguel-Rojas et al., 2009; Bohorquez et al., 2011; Pasquetti and Peres, 2015), or spinning motions (Jiménez-González et al., 2013, 2014). Their implementation in real problems usually requires an important power input, what limits somehow its applicability and efficiency and renders passive control systems more attractive because of their simplicity. Among other passive strategies, it is worth mentioning the works from Mair (1965) who studied the effect of including plates on the base of the body, Park et al. (2006) who introduced trailing edge modifications in the form of small tabs, those from Sanmiguel-Rojas et al. (2011); Cai and Chng (2009) and Kruiswyk and Dutton (1990) on the use of open base cavities or similarly Han et al. (1992); Mair (1978); Choi et al. (2014), on boat-tailed after-bodies. Besides, Martín-Alcántara et al. (2014) proposed a multi-cavity device that produces a maximum drag reduction of 25% at $Re = 20000$, obtaining additionally a less chaotic wake topology. Notwithstanding the aforementioned positive features, the performance of any type of rear cavity as a control mechanism is related to their depth, obtaining larger drag reductions as the cavity deepens (Sanmiguel-Rojas et al., 2011). In that sense, functionality requirements and practical geometrical limitations in vehicles usually restrict the depth, subsequently hindering its capability as control mechanism. Consequently, in order to overcome such limitations, it seems interesting to investigate any potential performance improvement of the addition of a base cavity with a fixed depth, for instance, by means of shape modification.

Most of the above investigations base the design of control strategies on the general knowledge of the physical mechanisms governing the flow around bluff bodies. Alternatively, the use of sensitivity analysis applied to flow control may help to precisely identify the regions which contribute the most to wake instability (Marquet et al., 2008; Meliga et al., 2012) or drag and lift generation (Meliga et al., 2014). This identification allows a more specific design and an optimal placement of control elements aiming at suppressing instabilities or reducing the drag, without having to carry out parametric studies or testing different locations empirically. In fact, these sensitivity analyses have been already satisfactorily proven, obtaining accurate predictions when compared with results from experimental work or numerical simulations (see e.g. Meliga et al., 2012; Parezanović and Cadot, 2012). Regarding aerodynamic forces, Meliga et al. (2014) have recently derived a linearized adjoint formulation to analyze the sensitivity of drag to local force perturbations on the flow around a square cylinder, for laminar and turbulent regimes. By simply introducing small control cylinders in those flow regions featuring the highest sensitivity, reductions up to 20% in the main drag were obtained. Consequently, this adjoint approach stands out as a powerful tool to maximize the drag reduction and to design optimized control devices. In that sense, adjoint-based optimization has long been recognized to be efficient for studies with large numbers of design variables, especially in the aerospace sector (Jameson, 1988; Burgreen and Baysal, 1996). In fact, Othmer (2014) has recently considered the use of adjoint shape optimization techniques applied to car aerodynamics, focusing on the reduction of drag force and using the open source computational fluid dynamics (CFD) toolbox OpenFOAM®. Interestingly, the combined use of sensitivity analysis and body topological modifications provides with efficient solutions for control devices or reduction of the aerodynamic forces acting on the body, which are achieved by means of iterative processes that characterize the sequential interactions between flow and structure. Since, in most applications, the geometry modifications are constrained by functionality and other requirements, it might be interesting to consider, as a solution for flow control and forces reduction, the implementation of control devices whose design stems from adjoint-based sensitivity and optimization analysis, what would ensure a high performance.

Following this idea, the present work explores the use of adjoint formulation to assess the sensitivity of drag to flow and structure topological modifications, in the wake behind a blunt-based body with a base cavity, which is a widespread configuration in real wake control applications (see e.g. Choi et al., 2014), in an attempt to evaluate the potential for improvement on the efficiency of rear cavities of fixed depth as passive control strategy. Thus, the study aims at achieving additional drag reduction on the wake behind a

two-dimensional bluff body of semi-ellipsoidal nose and straight rear cavity, by analyzing the effect of small control cylinders in the wake (Meliga et al., 2014) and optimal geometry modifications of the cavity structure (Othmer, 2008). The predictions of drag reduction obtained by means of the adjoint formulation analysis and topological modifications, will be compared with results from numerical simulations of the flow around the modifiedThe unsteady geometries, which will help appraising the suitability of the sensitivity analysis for wake control and aerodynamics enhancement. Thus, the problem formulation and numerical techniques employed are first described in Section 2. Section 3 is devoted to results, showing first those from the sensitivity analysis of drag to local force perturbations in the wake (Section 3.1), followed by the evaluation of the inclusion of control cylinders in the regions of highest sensitivity by means of numerical simulations. Next, in Section 3.2, we present results from the shape optimization of the straight rear cavity, based on the projection of drag sensitivity maps into the body surface. Then, three-dimensional numerical simulations are performed to show the impact of the latter structure modifications on the turbulent flow, whose results are presented in Section 3.3, where the main flow features are discussed for two different Reynolds numbers, $Re = 2000$ and $Re = 20000$. Finally, the main conclusions are drawn in Section 4.

2. Problem Description and Numerical Aspects

2.1. Flow configuration and governing equations

The three-dimensional turbulent flow of an incompressible free-stream of velocity U_∞ , density ρ and viscosity μ around a two-dimensional bluff body of semi-ellipsoidal nose is considered herein. Fig. 1 shows the scheme of the problem and computational domain, Ω , which aims to replicate the flow in a rectangular cross-section wind tunnel. The former domain is similar to those used in previous studies (Krajnović and Davidson, 2003; Pastoor et al., 2008; Guilmineau et al., 2011; Martín-Alcántara et al., 2014), and thus, appropriate for the present work. The body of height H , length $L = 3.83H$ and spanwise width $W = 7.64H$, is embedded by the lateral walls, thus avoiding any edge effect, and placed at the half-height of the computational domain. The body presents a streamlined front to avoid flow separation and is characterized by an ellipsoidal nose of major-to-minor-axes aspect ratio equal to 2. The front of the body is located $7.85H$ downstream from the inlet, whereas the domain outlet is placed at a distance of $21H$ downstream from the body base. The dimensions of the wind-tunnel considered as the computational domain are respectively $L_{wt} = 32.68H$, $H_{wt} = 21H$ and $W_{wt} = 7.64H$, with a geometric blockage of the model inside the numerical domain of approximately 5%. The body also implements a straight base cavity of depth $0.3H$ and wall thickness $0.05H$, similar to that proposed by Martín-Alcántara et al. (2014) and Evrard et al. (2016).

Figure 1: Scheme of the flow configuration and computational domain with the two-dimensional, semi-ellipsoidal body.

Under the above conditions, the characteristic length, velocity, time and pressure scales are respectively H , U_∞ , H/U_∞ and ρU_∞^2 . In the following, all variables will be made dimensionless using these scales.

Consequently, the Reynolds number is defined as $Re = \rho U_\infty H / \mu$, however, the dimensionless frequency will be $St = fh / U_\infty$, where f is a frequency and h , not necessarily equal to H , the distance between the upper and lower edges of the cavity walls.

As it has been previously outlined, the work can be divided into two different parts. A drag sensitivity study is first conducted, in which both the inclusion of control cylinders (Meliga et al., 2014) and the optimal shape geometrical modification (Othmer, 2008) of a base cavity device are subsequently analyzed in Section 2.2. For the sake of numerical feasibility, the flow is assumed to be two-dimensional in this part of the work. Secondly, in Section 2.3, the suitability in more realistic flows of this previously optimized shape is next evaluated, performing three-dimensional numerical simulations, which allow a complete characterization of the main wake features and drag reduction. For such studies, different numerical techniques and models have been used, which are next described.

2.2. Two-dimensional drag sensitivity response to localized flow perturbations

2.2.1. Theoretical formulation

With the aim at improving the performance of rear cavities as drag reduction devices, we perform a sensitivity analysis of the drag coefficient to modifications of the flow around the body under investigation (Fig. 1), induced by a localized control force, \mathbf{f} , which can be used to model the reacting forces generated by a small control cylinder placed near the body base, or any geometrical modification introduced on the body wall. For this purpose, we adopt the simplified adjoint-based steady analysis developed by Meliga et al. (2014), for unsteady flows, which is capable of retrieving the main information at the most sensitive regions around the body and the drag reduction values at the leading order. This simplified approach allows the determination of a steady sensitivity for unsteady flows, by only considering mean flow variables and the drag as a steady function of such mean variables. Thus, for any given unsteady physical variable, such as the pressure, $p = \bar{p} + p'$, where \bar{p} represents its time-averaged mean value, defined as

$$\bar{p} = \frac{1}{\tau} \int_0^\tau p \, dt, \quad (1)$$

being τ a sufficiently large averaging time to allow statistical equilibrium, and p' its fluctuation, with $\bar{p}' = 0$. Hence, the mean drag coefficient, \bar{C}_d , can be expressed as

$$\bar{C}_d = \frac{2\bar{F}_x}{\rho U_\infty^2 HW} = \frac{2 \left[- \int_{\Sigma_b} (\bar{p}\mathbf{n}) \cdot \mathbf{e}_x dl + \int_{\Sigma_b} \mu (\nabla^2 \bar{\mathbf{u}} \cdot \mathbf{n}) \mathbf{e}_x dl \right]}{\rho U_\infty^2 HW}, \quad (2)$$

where \bar{F}_x is the time-averaged mean value of the axial component of the force acting on the body, $\bar{\mathbf{u}}$ is the time-averaged velocity vector, and \mathbf{e}_x is the unit outward axial vector at the body surface.

In a first order approximation, the mean drag variation $\delta\bar{C}_d$ induced by an infinitesimal control force $\delta\mathbf{f}$ is estimated by means of

$$\delta\bar{C}_d = (\nabla_f \bar{C}_d \mid \delta\bar{\mathbf{f}}), \quad (3)$$

where $\nabla_f \bar{C}_d$ is the mean drag sensitivity function, $\delta\bar{\mathbf{f}}$ accounts for the mean component of the control force, and (\mid) denotes the L_2 inner product in the space domain, Ω ,

$$(\mathbf{u}_1 \mid \mathbf{u}_2) = \int_\Omega \mathbf{u}_1 \cdot \mathbf{u}_2 \, dx dy. \quad (4)$$

This simplified approach excludes the effects of the fluctuating component $\delta\mathbf{f}'$, and the mean flow correction through the coupling with fluctuating motion and the generation of Reynolds stresses (Maurel et al., 1995). However, Meliga et al. (2014) showed that the most sensitive regions are satisfactorily characterized, since control acts fundamentally via the mean component of the forcing in the flow around a bluff body, even for turbulent regimes. Therefore, we adopt such strategy for our calculations, in order to identify potential improvements on the performance of the body base cavity, since it represents a good compromise between accurate predictions and limited computational cost.

<i>Mesh</i>	Number of cells (n)	\overline{C}_d	$\xi_{C_d}(\%)$	St_{C_d}	$\xi_{St_{C_d}}(\%)$
# 1	$\sim 0.6 \times 10^5$	0.737	1.55	0.439	1.86
# 2	$\sim 1.0 \times 10^5$	0.750	0.23	0.434	0.46
# 3	$\sim 1.4 \times 10^5$	0.750	0.23	0.433	0.23
# 4	$\sim 1.8 \times 10^5$	0.751	-	0.432	-

Table 1: Grid sensitivity analysis for the two-dimensional simulations around a bluff body at $Re = 2000$. Comparison among the values of the mean drag coefficient \overline{C}_d and vortex shedding Strouhal number, St_{C_d} , obtained from the temporal evolution of $C_d(t)$, using four different grids. The relative error, ξ , is calculated with respect to mesh #4, which features the largest number of cells, n .

The mean drag sensitivity $\nabla_f \overline{C}_d$ is thus obtained by solving a Lagrangian formalism (see Meliga et al., 2014, for details), which considers the drag as the cost function to be minimized, subject to the control variable \mathbf{f} , i.e. the forcing, and satisfying the steady governing equations stemming by linearly disturbing the mean basic flow $(\overline{\mathbf{u}}, \overline{p})$, whose time-averaged mean variations are accounted by $(\delta \overline{\mathbf{u}}, \delta \overline{p})$. This linear *direct* system reads,

$$\nabla \cdot \delta \overline{\mathbf{u}} = 0, \quad \nabla \delta \overline{\mathbf{u}} \cdot \overline{\mathbf{u}} + \nabla \overline{\mathbf{u}} \cdot \delta \overline{\mathbf{u}} + \nabla \delta \overline{p} - \nabla \cdot \left(\frac{1}{Re_t} \nabla \delta \overline{\mathbf{u}} \right) = \delta \overline{\mathbf{f}} \quad \text{in } \Omega, \quad (5)$$

$$\delta \overline{\mathbf{u}} = 0 \quad \text{in } \Sigma_b. \quad (6)$$

where $Re_t = U_\infty H / \nu$ is the turbulent Reynolds number and the effective kinematic viscosity ν is the sum of the molecular and the turbulent viscosities. In Eqs.(5) and (6) all infinitesimal terms, $\delta \overline{\mathbf{u}}$ and $\delta \overline{p}$, are approximations to the mean flow disturbance components.

The sensitivity $\nabla_f \overline{C}_d$ is then obtained by using a variational technique aiming at computing Lagrange multipliers, $\overline{\mathbf{u}}^\dagger$ and \overline{p}^\dagger , which hold, in principle, no physical meaning, and are chosen in such a way that variations of the Lagrangian functional with respect to the direct system variables, $(\overline{\mathbf{u}}, \overline{p})$, vanishes. Thus, it can be demonstrated that

$$\nabla_f \overline{C}_d = \overline{\mathbf{u}}^\dagger, \quad (7)$$

where $\overline{\mathbf{u}}^\dagger$ is, along with \overline{p}^\dagger , the solution of the linear *adjoint* system,

$$\nabla \cdot \overline{\mathbf{u}}^\dagger = 0, \quad -\nabla \overline{\mathbf{u}}^\dagger \cdot \overline{\mathbf{u}} + (\nabla \overline{\mathbf{u}})^T \cdot \overline{\mathbf{u}}^\dagger - \nabla \overline{p}^\dagger - \nabla \cdot \left(\frac{1}{Re_t} \nabla \overline{\mathbf{u}}^\dagger \right) = 0 \quad \text{in } \Omega, \quad (8)$$

$$\overline{\mathbf{u}}^\dagger = 2\mathbf{e}_x \quad \text{on } \Sigma_b, \quad (9)$$

and will be, in the following, referred to as adjoint velocity and pressure respectively, due to the similarities between both direct and adjoint systems.

The solution of the adjoint system (8)-(9), requires the previous knowledge of the time-averaged mean flow variables, $(\overline{\mathbf{u}}, \overline{p})$, i.e. the basic flow, which can be obtained from numerical simulations. In that sense, we have initially performed a numerical study of the turbulent flow around the body described in Section 2.1, as a first step to assess the drag sensitivity of the basic flow. We have limited our study to a low value of Reynolds number, i.e. $Re = 2000$, in order to minimize the deviation of the simplified Eq.(3) from the total drag variation that would be obtained if the feeding of force fluctuations through the Reynolds stresses were considered. To this end, incompressible turbulent unsteady two-dimensional simulations have been performed using OpenFOAM® open source finite-volume toolbox, by implementing a RANS (Reynolds Averaged Navier-Stokes equations) $k - \omega$ model to obtain the basic flow. Besides, appropriate boundary conditions have been used, namely, a uniform fluid stream of velocity $(U_\infty, 0, 0)$, with a turbulent intensity of 1% and a characteristic turbulent length scale of $0.1H$ has been imposed at the inlet, Σ_i , whereas an outflow boundary condition, $p(\mathbf{x}, t) = \mathbf{n} \cdot \nabla \mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}, t) = 0$, has been applied at the outlet, Σ_o . In addition, a no-slip condition has been set, $\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}, t) = 0$, at the remaining wall boundaries, i.e. at the body, Σ_b , and lateral walls, Σ_w . We have used

second order upwind and Green-Gauss linear centered discretization schemes for the spatial terms, a Crank-Nicholson scheme for the time integration, while the pressure-velocity coupling has been treated through the Pressure-Implicit Split-Operator (PISO) algorithm (Issa, 1986), ensuring that the Courant-Friedrichs-Lewy (CFL) number was always below 0.5. In addition, a grid sensitivity study has been carried out for four different meshes, focusing on the time-averaged drag coefficient, $\overline{C_d}$, and the corresponding Strouhal number of the periodic structures shed behind the body (see Table 1). To this aim, the number of nodes in the axial and vertical directions have been monotonically increased, thus improving the resolution, specially in the near wake and body edges. As an outcome, a mesh consisting of 1.8×10^5 cells, i.e. mesh #4, has been selected to perform the simulations, which features a maximum y^+ value of one. Once the simulations have been conducted, we compute the time-averaged mean magnitudes of velocity and pressure, $\overline{\mathbf{u}}$ and \overline{p} , according to Eq. (1). For that purpose, 80 shedding cycles have been averaged once the vortex-shedding regime was established.

After the computation of the direct mean flow variables, we solve the linear adjoint system (8)-(9), adopted to RANS modelling, using the computational domain and mesh described above, implementing an incompressible steady RANS adjoint linear solver in OpenFOAM® (Nilsson et al., 2014), which employs second order spatial discretization schemes and a SIMPLE algorithm for the pressure-velocity coupling, and makes use of the frozen turbulence assumption to close the adjoint equations, i.e. the Reynolds stress is unperturbed. The latter means that the adjoint system takes the value of the primal (direct) turbulence viscosity, which is a source of inaccuracies in the turbulent regions (Othmer, 2008), although in the present case it is acceptable since we are dealing with transitional flows (Zymaris et al., 2009). The use of this solver has been limited to obtain the adjoint variables, without performing any shape modification by neglecting the source porosity term (Nilsson et al., 2014). Thus, as adjoint boundary conditions, we set nil adjoint velocity at the inlet Σ_i , $\mathbf{u}^\dagger(\mathbf{x}, t) = 0$, no-slip conditions at Σ_w and Σ_b , $\mathbf{u}^\dagger(\mathbf{x}, t) = 0$, and an outflow condition at the outlet Σ_o , $p^\dagger(\mathbf{x}, t) = \mathbf{n} \cdot \nabla \mathbf{u}^\dagger(\mathbf{x}, t) = 0$. In addition, a grid sensitivity study has been conducted considering the meshes in Table 1. The results showed no variation on the distribution of the drag sensitivity to localized forcing, $\nabla_f \overline{C_d}$, from mesh #2. Thus, mesh #4 has been used to ensure the accuracy of the results. Further validation of the adjoint solver is provided in Section 3.1 by comparing the results of sensitivity and drag variation, induced by a small control cylinder, for the flow around a square cylinder (see Fig. 2), with those obtained by Meliga et al. (2014). In addition, results from the sensitivity analysis applied to the bluff body considered in the present work have been also validated with two-dimensional simulations. In that sense, once the linearized adjoint problem is solved and the values of $\overline{\mathbf{u}}^\dagger$ and \overline{p}^\dagger are known, the sensitivity of the mean drag to localized forcing is retrieved by means of $\overline{\mathbf{u}}^\dagger$, what allows a precise prediction of regions in which forcing or shape modification could have a larger impact on the mean drag. Finally, the mean drag variation can be easily obtained using Eq. (3), provided that $\delta \mathbf{f}$ is known (for instance, by modeling the reacting force exerted by a control cylinder).

2.2.2. Body shape optimization

As mentioned earlier, the drag sensitivity distribution provides with a clear indication of what type of flow modifications, induced by any local forcing, have a largest effect on the aerodynamic forces. Following that idea, body shape modifications based on the drag sensitivity distribution offer an interesting solution to improve the cavity performance as control strategy, when the depth is restricted, and without having to add external devices, e.g. cylinders. To perform such task, we use the topological optimization algorithm, which governs the body shape deformation based on the aerodynamic shape sensitivities of the drag force, that are used as an input to guide the geometrical modifications of the body base. Following Othmer (2014) and references therein, the drag shape sensitivity on the body surface can be computed as

$$\frac{\partial C_d}{\partial \beta} = -\frac{1}{Re_t} \frac{\partial \mathbf{u}^\dagger}{\partial n} \cdot \frac{\partial \mathbf{u}}{\partial n}, \quad (10)$$

where β denotes the normal displacement of the surface node, $\partial/\partial n$ stands for the normal derivative, and \mathbf{u}^\dagger and \mathbf{u} represent respectively the instantaneous adjoint and direct velocities. The shape sensitivity identifies the regions where normal surface displacements result into decreasing (resp. increasing) drag coefficient, when modifications occur in the same (resp. opposite) direction of shape sensitivity map. Thus, the body shape optimizations can be done by coupling the previously described adjoint solver with a standard deformation tool, by mapping the shape sensitivity for each surface node into the morphing control points of the deformation algorithm. The implementation of this coupling process has been done with the optimization toolbox

<i>Mesh</i>	Number of cells (n)	\overline{C}_d	$\xi_{C_d}(\%)$	St_{C_d}	$\xi_{St_{C_d}}(\%)$
# 1	$\sim 0.5 \times 10^5$	0.796	1.49	0.429	5.97
# 2	$\sim 1.0 \times 10^6$	0.819	1.41	0.444	2.92
# 3	$\sim 2.5 \times 10^6$	0.818	1.33	0.449	1.82
# 4	$\sim 4.0 \times 10^6$	0.808	-	0.457	-

Table 2: Grid sensitivity analysis for the three-dimensional simulations around a bluff body at $Re = 2000$. Comparison among the values of the mean drag coefficient \overline{C}_d and vortex shedding Strouhal number, St_{C_d} , obtained using four different grids. The relative error, ξ , is calculated with respect to mesh #4, which features the largest number of cells, n .

implemented in ANSYS Fluent® (www.ansys.com), which allows free-form deformation of control points in a very controlled way. This free-form morphing tool is based on Bernstein polynomials, defined relative to a set of control points, for which a smooth deformation occurs by moving some of them by following the gradient of sensitivity in accordance with the steepest descent method (Han et al., 2011). This combined use of Bernstein polynomial interpolation and a coarser deformation grid smooths out the sensitivity field and mitigates the effect of any unbounded values (Palacios et al., 2015), that the presence of sharp edges might cause (Jameson, 1988; Mao, 2015), providing fairly good results as will be later demonstrated in Section 3.3.

The procedure employed in the present study consists in running the adjoint solver described earlier, using as input the primal flow variables calculated from the RANS numerical simulations, i.e. \mathbf{u} , p , k and ω ; to obtain \mathbf{u}^\dagger and p^\dagger . These adjoint variables are read by the optimization tool to implement a drag shape sensitivity analysis (Eq. 10) and to perform shape modifications through the definition of control points boxes. Since we are interested in the optimal cavity geometrical modification to reduce the drag, the control box is defined around the cavity (see Fig. 5a). This control grid is made up of $n_x \times n_y$ points, where $n_x = 100$ and $n_y = 80$ are respectively the number of control points in the x and y directions. In particular, our study aims at carrying out subsequent iterations leading to slight cavity shape modifications, by means of progressive control mesh morphing, whose maximum displacement for each iteration is limited to the size of characteristic control mesh cell. Thus, after several steps, a final shape is obtained, for which further changes do not achieve any relevant additional drag reduction. At this point, the outcome could be considered an optimum. In that sense, as it will be detailed in Section 3.2, the analysis will be done through successive *one-shot* optimizations (Othmer, 2014), which consists in obtaining converged solutions of time-dependent direct flow quantities, and in computing for a selected instant, adjoint variables and shape sensitivity, whereupon the corresponding shape modification is performed. Next, another RANS numerical simulation around the modified body is performed, to verify the drag reduction after solution convergence and to obtain again the direct flow variables, from which a new iteration starts. Further details on this iterative, *optimizing* process will be given in Section 3.2, where final and intermediate forms, and changes experienced by drag coefficient in successive iterations are presented.

2.3. Three-dimensional flow simulations

To conclude the optimization process of the body base cavity, the shape obtained from the drag sensitivity analysis is assessed and compared with the original body through three-dimensional turbulent unsteady simulations. The whole computational domain is thus accounted, being the simulations conducted in OpenFOAM®. Thus, the two-dimensional results are verified and the main features characterizing the new flow are presented and discussed. These simulations have been performed for the originally considered $Re = 2000$ and also extended to $Re = 20000$. To this aim, the IDDES (Improved Delayed Detached Simulations) turbulence model has been used. This numerical approach is a hybrid RANS-LES (Large Eddy Simulation) model (Fröhlich and von Terzi, 2008), suitable for the simulation of massively separated flows (Shur et al., 2008). Consequently, a RANS simulation is conducted in the attached wall boundary layer, whereas the LES model is activated within the flow core, in the separated flow regions, which results in an intricate but powerful approach for the study of these kinds of flows. Thus, the IDDES model allows to resolve accurately the large scales in the wake region through the LES model, while the RANS model, specifically the Spalart-Allmaras model, is used in the near wall region, with the subsequent computational cost saving. Furthermore, with respect to the near wall treatment, a Van Driest’s law, (van Driest, 1956) has been used. The main advantage of such

Figure 2: (a) Spatial distribution of the mean drag coefficient sensitivity, $\nabla_f \bar{C}_d$, for a square cylinder at $Re = 100$ (contours of the sensitivity magnitude and streamlines of the adjoint velocity). (b) Total drag variation of the two cylinder system, $\delta \bar{C}_{d,T}(x_c, y_c)$, formed by the square cylinder and a control cylinder of diameter $\Theta = 0.1$. Thick solid lines represent the separatrix of the recirculation region.

unified law of the wall is that the first grid point close to the wall can be placed into the buffer or viscous region, $y^+ < 30$, without the loss of accuracy associated with logarithmic approaches. Regarding boundary conditions, as in the two-dimensional simulations, a uniform fluid stream of velocity $(U_\infty, 0, 0)$, with a turbulent intensity of 1% and a characteristic turbulent length scale of $0.1H$ has been imposed at the inlet, Σ_i , whereas an outflow boundary condition, $p(\mathbf{x}, t) = \mathbf{n} \cdot \nabla \mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}, t) = 0$, has been applied at the outlet, Σ_o . In addition, a no-slip condition has been set, $\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}, t) = 0$, at the remaining wall boundaries, i.e. at the body, Σ_b , and lateral walls, Σ_w . Besides, a second order Gauss Linear central differentiation scheme (Lax and Wendroff, 1960) has been used for the spatial terms, while a second order implicit Euler method backward scheme is employed for the temporal terms (Geurts, 2004). The PIMPLE algorithm (a combination of the PISO and SIMPLE algorithms) has been selected for the pressure-velocity coupling, allowing the use of relatively large time-steps. In addition, a maximum CFL number lower than 1 has been considered to set the time step, which results in a dimensionless time step $\Delta t = 0.008$. Moreover, in all cases, the analysis of frequencies and global time-averaged variables have been done considering at least 700 characteristic periods, i.e. $t \simeq 1600$, once the flow conditions become statistically converged, with no differences reported when using longer averaging periods. Moreover, as it was done for the two-dimensional study, a grid convergence study has been also performed (see Table 2). Differences below 1.5% in the value of \bar{C}_d are observed in all cases, whereas in the case of the characteristic Strouhal number, these are lower than 2% for the two finer grids. Consequently, mesh #3, consisting of 2.5×10^6 cells, has been considered for the three-dimensional computations, due to its best accuracy-to-computational cost ratio. Finally, it must be said that the latter grid presents a $\max(y^+)$ of order unity.

3. Results and discussion

We present now results obtained from the different studies described in Section 2. We will start with the computation of drag sensitivity, and subsequent wake control using two types of local forcing, i.e. small control cylinder, as done in Meliga et al. (2014), and smooth cavity structure deformation, performed using the aforementioned topological optimization algorithm; for the flow around the two-dimensional body at $Re = 2000$. Next, in order to validate the performance of our methodology, and to quantify the drag reduction achieved in a more realistic regime when *optimized* rear cavities are used, we will analyze the topology and dynamics of the flow around the three-dimensional body for $Re = 2000$ and $Re = 20000$, obtained from numerical simulations implementing a hybrid IDDES turbulence model.

3.1. Sensitivity of mean drag to localized forcing

As discussed in Section 2.2, we adopt the simplified steady sensitivity approach for unsteady flows developed by Meliga et al. (2014), focusing on the time-averaged mean drag sensitivity, which is obtained using Eq. (7),

after solving the adjoint linear system (8)-(9) with the help of the corresponding linear adjoint solver. In particular, we applied the method to the unsteady flow at $Re = 2000$, using values of time-averaged mean velocity and pressure, $\bar{\mathbf{u}}$ and \bar{p} , previously obtained from unsteady RANS simulations. Before investigating the present flow configuration, shown in Fig. 1, we computed the drag sensitivity for the flow around a square cylinder of side H at $Re = 100$, with the aim at comparing results with those included in Meliga et al. (2014) and consequently, validate our numerical procedure. In that sense, Fig. 2(a) depicts the mean drag sensitivity distribution, being its magnitude defined by color levels while streamlines indicate the orientation of the sensitivity gradient, indicating that, to decrease the drag, the control force must be oriented in the opposite direction of streamlines arrows. Although the shear layer regions and the recirculation bubble (enclosed by the thick solid line) feature important sensitivity, higher magnitudes are achieved in the front part due the body's bluff form, suggesting that any forcing, either through shape modification or control cylinder placement, should be applied upstream from the body to render the flow more *streamlined*. In that regard, Fig. 2(b) shows the total mean drag variation as a function of the position of a small control cylinder of diameter $\Theta = 0.1$. To obtain such map, the reacting force of the small cylinder, whose location is defined by (x_c, y_c) , is modeled using the following equation (Meliga et al., 2014),

$$\delta\bar{\mathbf{f}}(x, y) = -\frac{1}{2}\Theta C_{d\Theta}(Re_\Theta)\boldsymbol{\zeta}(x_c, y_c)\delta(x - x_c, y - y_c), \quad (11)$$

being $C_{d\Theta} = 0.8558 + 10.05Re_\Theta^{-0.7084}$ the drag coefficient of the control cylinder, $Re_\Theta = \Theta\|\bar{\mathbf{u}}\|(x_c, y_c)Re$ the local Reynolds number based on Θ (denoting $\|\cdot\|$ the inner product norm), and $\boldsymbol{\zeta}(x_c, y_c) = \|\bar{\mathbf{u}}\|\bar{\mathbf{u}}$. Thus, the total drag variation $\delta\bar{C}_{d,T}$ of the combined system of square and control cylinders, whose map is depicted in Fig. 2(b), is obtained by means of Eqs. (3) and (11) as,

$$\delta\bar{C}_{d,T}(x_c, y_c) = (\bar{\mathbf{u}}^\dagger|\delta\bar{\mathbf{f}}_d) = -\frac{1}{2}\Theta C_{d\Theta}(\bar{\mathbf{u}}^\dagger(x_c, y_c) - 2\mathbf{e}_x) \cdot \boldsymbol{\zeta}(x_c, y_c), \quad (12)$$

from which it can be inferred that drag reduction is most efficient in the region located along the symmetry axis, upstream from the body, as foreseen in the previous sensitivity distribution analysis. More interestingly, the drag reduction map depicted in Fig. 2(b) is qualitative and quantitatively identical to that computed by Meliga et al. (2014) (see Fig. 12 therein), therefore validating our methodology and numerical schemes. Hence, in the following we will apply such analysis to the flow configuration sketched in Fig. 1.

Figure 3 shows the mean drag sensitivity for the slender bluff body with rear cavity at $Re = 2000$, along with the total drag variation induced by a control cylinder of diameter $\Theta = 0.016$, computed using Eq. (11). The cylinder size has been selected by considering that the maximum local Reynolds number based on its diameter is approximately 40, hence below the critical one giving rise to vortex shedding in the flow. As expected, the more streamlined shape of the bluff body of ellipsoidal nose, provides with lower values of sensitivity magnitude than those featured by the square cylinder case. Interestingly, highest magnitudes are reached at the rear edges of the cavity, although the shear layer and recirculation regions also show intermediate values of sensitivity. These results suggest that the forcing should be applied close to the cavity edges or inside the recirculation bubble in order to achieve largest drag reduction, what is confirmed by the total drag variation map depicted in Fig. 3(b). The reduction associated to the placement of a control cylinder in the near wake may be related to a larger base pressure coefficient and a weaker backflow, while a cylinder placed close to the cavity edge should affect the shear layer detachment. Thus, since we are interested in improving the performance of cavities as control devices, we explore the latter scenario in order to quantify potential drag reduction and to evaluate flow modifications leading to such outcome, when control cylinders are placed close to the rear edge, in the most sensitive areas identified in Fig. 3(a).

As suggested by the sensitivity distribution in Fig. 3(a), in order to achieve largest drag reductions, we placed two small cylinders of diameter $\Theta = 0.016$ at two symmetric positions close to the cavity edge, within the areas of high sensitivity and in locations where the cylinder reacting force opposes the gradient streamlines plotted therein, i.e. $(x_c, y_c) = (0.368, \pm 0.428)$. Interestingly, Parezanović and Cadot (2012) identified a similar location, as a transition region between *inner shear* and *mid-shear* zones, where the introduction of a localized forcing, by means of a single control cylinder, gives rise to important base pressure increase and overall drag reduction, regardless of cylinder size. Consequently, similar effects are expected for the present

Figure 3: (a) Spatial distribution of the mean drag coefficient sensitivity, $\nabla_f \overline{C}_d$, for the bluff body under investigation at $Re = 2000$ (contours of the sensitivity magnitude and streamlines of the adjoint velocity). (b) Total drag variation, $\delta \overline{C}_{d,T}(x_c, y_c)$, of the system formed by the bluff body and a control cylinder of diameter $\Theta = 0.016$. Thick solid lines represent the separatrix of the recirculation region.

Case	$\min[\overline{C}_p(t)]$	L_{rec}	$\min[\overline{u}_x(t)]$	L_f	$\overline{C}_d(t)$
Uncontrolled	-0.372	1.53	-0.150	2.783	0.752
Controlled	-0.370	1.55	-0.148	2.821	0.747

Table 3: Comparison between the global time-averaged magnitudes: minimum pressure coefficient, $\min(\overline{C}_p)$, recirculation length, L_{rec} , minimum recirculation velocity $\min(\overline{u}_x)$, vortex formation length L_f , and drag \overline{C}_d , obtained from simulations of the two time-averaged flows under investigation, i.e. natural flow around the bluff body and controlled flow placing small cylinders close to the cavity edge.

symmetric configuration of the improved cavity. Thus, in a preliminary step, we first analyze qualitative and quantitative changes in wake dynamics and drag reduction, using unsteady RANS turbulent simulations results at $Re = 2000$. In that line, Table 3 lists the values of different global variables of the time-averaged flow for the natural wake and that controlled by placing two small cylinders near the cavity edge. First, it is shown that the minimum base static pressure level, i.e. $\min(\overline{C}_p(t))$, increases when the symmetric pair of cylinders are introduced in the flow (controlled wake). This lower overall level is accompanied by an increase in the length of the recirculating region behind the body, L_{rec} , from which it can be inferred that the axial velocity gradient is reduced, and consequently the backflow decreases as well, as the values of $\min(\overline{u}_x(t))$ show. Besides, the increase in the base pressure is directly related to a smaller mean drag, which in our case decreases from 0.752 to 0.747, representing a 0.6% drop approximately. This slight drag decrease corresponds to a numerically estimated drag sensitivity of 1.923, which is similar to that predicted using the Eq. (11), at the selected location $(x_c, y_c) = (0.368, \pm 0.428)$, which amounts to 1.716 approximately. Although the results are fairly close, this 11% relative difference indicates that the use of non infinitesimally small cylinders may render the linear assumption quantitatively inaccurate, thus being the use of more complex, nonlinear adjoint schemes more appropriate to estimate the forcing effect (Mao et al., 2015). The effect of including control cylinders on the drag coefficient has been also verified through three dimensional simulations, which provide with a reduction of 0.9%. This value lies within the range given by the sensitivity analysis and the two dimensional simulations, suggesting that the simple model of Eqs. (11)-(12) can be used to estimate the drag variation. However, the drag reduction obtained using small control cylinders is almost negligible in this case and, therefore, more efficient mechanisms need to be implemented to achieve drag reductions of practical interest, as described in Section 3.2.

Besides, regarding the wake instability, since a strong backflow is known to promote local absolute instability (Monkewitz, 1988), what is connected to global instability in wakes (Pier, 2008), the latter flow modifications should translate not only into a drag reduction, but also into a weakening of fluctuation amplitude in the temporal evolution of the drag, $C_d(t)$, if this amplitude is viewed, in a rough approximation, as a quantitative estimator of the wake global unstable dynamics. At this point, it should be noted that at $Re = 2000$ the dynamics is far from the threshold of unsteadiness in terms of Re , and consequently is highly non-linear, so that it cannot be accurately interpreted only in terms of global linear modes. However, weaker fluctuations of $C_d(t)$ would clearly suggest that the wake global dynamics is becoming less unstable, and the oscillator

Figure 4: (a) Time-evolution of the drag coefficient, $C_d(t)$, and the mean constant values, $\overline{C_d(t)}$, obtained from simulations of the two flows under investigation: natural flow around the bluff body (black dashed line) and controlled flow using small cylinders placed close to the cavity edge (red solid line); and (b) corresponding Power Spectral Density, $\text{PSD}(St)$ (arbitrary units), of the drag coefficient fluctuations, $C_d(t)' = C_d(t) - \overline{C_d(t)}$, for the two aforementioned cases.

behavior of the flow is being attenuated when the cylinders are used. To check this hypothesis, we include in Fig. 4(a) temporal signals of $C_d(t)$ for the two wakes compared, i.e. natural and controlled flow, along with the corresponding Power Spectral Density distribution, $\text{PSD}(St)$, of drag fluctuations, $C_d(t)' = C_d(t) - \overline{C_d(t)}$ in Fig. 4(b). First, the aforementioned mean drag reduction induced by cylinders is clearly observed in Fig. 4(a), which is accompanied by an additional reduction in the magnitude of drag oscillations, $C_d(t)'$, what denotes a weakening of the flow unsteadiness and the intensity of shedding vortices (not shown here for the sake of conciseness). Consequently, the identification of sensitive areas also provides with valuable information on the wake control possibilities in terms of global mode dynamics. In fact, in order to quantify such weakening of drag oscillations, we compute the squared amplitude of fluctuations, $|A|_{C_d(t)'}^2$, through integration of the main peak in the $\text{PSD}(St)$, around the fundamental shedding frequency St_{C_d} (Fig. 4b), as

$$|A|_{C_d(t)'}^2 = \int_{St_{C_d} - \Delta St_d}^{St_{C_d} + \Delta St_u} \text{PSD}(St) dSt, \quad (13)$$

where ΔSt_d and ΔSt_u stand for the interval around St_{C_d} for which the energy drops to 2% the peak value. Such calculation allows us to estimate the reduction of oscillations amplitude in a value of 47% for the case at hand.

In general, these effects induced by the control cylinders can be interpreted in terms of the mechanisms described by Parezanović and Cadot (2012), and proposed by Gerrard (1966), whereby the placement of the cylinder in the inner shear tends to thin and reattach the primary shear layer of the blunt body. Consequently, the entrainment of the detached shear layer is reduced in the recirculation region and, as a result, the length of the formation region of the vortex street, enclosed by the eddies roll-up, increases (see values of L_f in Table 3). The enlargement of the formation length leads to a subsequent base pressure increase (i.e. drag reduction) and weaker pressure and velocity gradients, resulting into a lower radial shear and reverse flow. Moreover, sensitivity analysis by Parezanović and Cadot (2012) and Meliga et al. (2012) also showed that the inner shear region features a positive sensitivity to shedding frequency, so that the placement of a control cylinder within this area leads to a slight increase of the characteristic shedding frequency, St_{C_d} . The presence of control cylinders close to the cavity edges entails positive flow modifications in terms of drag and wake control. However, the drag reduction achieved is barely noticeable, what precluded us from further exploring this way as a strategy to improve rear cavities performance. Hence, we investigate next the effect on the forces and wake variables of cavity topological modifications, based on the sensitivity distributions computed in Section 3.1. Moreover, from a practical view, this different strategy would not imply the implementation of an additional set-up for the cylinder, what could be also considered an advantage. Nevertheless, its feasibility has to be yet investigated.

3.2. Drag variation by means of geometry optimization

As mentioned in Section 1, the performance of rear cavities as wake and drag control devices is highly dependent on their depth, which in most applications is limited by geometrical and functional requirements. Thus, we now investigate the suitability of cavity shape modifications as a solution to extend the potential for drag reduction when the cavity depth is fixed. After satisfactorily evaluating the viability of sensitivity analysis to predict mean drag and wake oscillations reduction when external control cylinders are implemented, we further explore the applicability of the adjoint-based approach described in Section 2.2.2 to the cavity topological optimization, where a drag reduction larger than that obtained with control cylinders is expected. To do so, we employ the optimization toolbox of ANSYS Fluent[®], which allows a free-form deformation of control box points. In that sense, since we are only interested in the optimal design of the cavity walls, we limit the structural optimization to the control area depicted in Fig. 5(a), which comprises $n_x = 100 \times n_y = 80$ control points, whose movement is determined by the steepest descent criterion.

Besides, the *optimal* shape calculation is accomplished by means of iterative computations of primal and adjoint flow variables, as mentioned in Section 2.2.2. As highlighted by Othmer (2014), accurate computation of adjoint to time-dependent primal variables is not feasible in complex problems due to the large storage requirements for the backward integration, so that only two approaches are usually employed, namely, the computation of sensitivity based on time-averaged primal variables and the implementation of one-shot optimizations for a frozen single instant, for which both primal and adjoint variables are obtained. As shown by Meliga et al. (2014), instantaneous sensitivity may provide with larger values than time-averaged flows (see Figs. 4 and 6 therein), especially when the vortex is being shed from the body edge. Consequently, in order to speed up the shape modification process, we choose to perform one-shot instantaneous optimizations for instants of alternate highest sensitivity near the cavity for each wall, identifying vortex shedding events in each side. Fig. 5(b) illustrates the optimization process in terms of normalized drag, $C_d(t)/\bar{C}_d^0$, where \bar{C}_d^0 is the mean drag coefficient of the body with a straight cavity. For each iteration, defined by a prescribed shape, we first compute a converged time-dependent regime of the primal flow, by means of RANS numerical simulations. Once the flow regime is established, i.e. when the time variation of drag coefficient in Fig. 5(b) is statistically converged, the values of \mathbf{u} , p , k and ω for the selected instant of largest sensitivity are plugged into the adjoint RANS solver in order to calculate the adjoint variables, \mathbf{u}^\dagger and p^\dagger , assuming the frozen turbulence simplification. Afterwards, the variables are used by the optimization toolbox to compute shape sensitivity (Eq. 10) and perform the shape modification, following the steepest descent method. Once the new shape is obtained, the process is repeated, alternating the side of the cavity for which the highest sensitivity is reached, until an approximately constant value of mean drag is obtained and no further optimization is possible.

Using the latter strategy, a converged shape is obtained after approximately 40 iterations, as shown in Fig. 5(b) for the case of $Re = 2000$, for which a mean drag reduction of approximately 23% is achieved, being considerably larger than that obtained earlier through the control cylinders. In this figure, each iteration corresponds to converged simulations performed with different shapes during the geometrical optimization process. Since the optimization is accomplished using instantaneous sensitivity maps featuring the largest magnitude, the process is guided locally in each iteration, and the shape modifications are mostly concentrated around the cavity edges. However, the successive iterations allow an overall and quick optimization of the shape that can be considered as a global optimum, as explained below. As example, we show in Fig. 6 the spatial distributions of the largest instantaneous drag sensitivity to forcing (top half in each panel), i.e. adjoint velocity magnitude, and the corresponding primal axial velocity (bottom half), along with the streamlines of the underlying adjoint and primal velocity vectors; for four different solutions of the shape optimization process. First, Fig. 6(a) shows the drag sensitivity for the initial shape, whose magnitude is larger than that characterizing the time-averaged drag sensitivity in Fig. 3(a), being the locus of highest magnitude concentrated around the rear edge. When the shape sensitivity is obtained (Eq. 10) the larger values on the rear edge will give rise to bigger control points shift in the surrounding area, configuring a new shape subject to a lower drag and featuring a weaker drag sensitivity, since the potential for drag reduction has now also decreased. This can be observed in Fig. 6(b) for the intermediate shape #1, corresponding to the outcome of the fifteenth

Figure 5: Shape optimization of the rear cavity at $Re = 2000$: (a) control volume for free-form morphing, being $n_x = 100$ and $n_y = 80$ the number of control points in each direction; and (b) progressive reduction of the normalized drag $C_d(t)/C_d^0$ upon successive one-shot optimizations. In Fig. 5(b) one out of every two iterations is shown for clarity.

iteration in Fig. 5(b), computing the sensitivity again after obtaining a converged solution of the RANS primal numerical simulations around the body. As expected, the sensitivity magnitude is clearly lower than that for the initial case (Fig. 6a), and now its maximum is slightly displaced towards the lee side of the edge. In general, a lower drag sensitivity and, consequently, its corresponding weaker shape sensitivity, will induce a smoother displacement of control points per iteration. In fact, Fig. 6(c) depicts the intermediate shape #2, obtained after twenty-five iterations, that features a pronounced curvature towards the inner side of the base cavity, which again provides with lower magnitude of drag sensitivity to forcing. This hollow cavity entails a local recirculation of the flow, as the distribution of primal velocity shows, that leads to a closer attachment of the boundary layer along the cavity wall and an increase in the curvature of the streamlines. Consequently, the flow leaves the cavity edge with a higher momentum toward the axis in the y coordinate. This configuration, defined by the formation of the vortex ring upstream from the edge, is further promoted during the last stages of the optimization process, as Fig. 6(d) shows. The final shape, reached after 40 iterations, can be considered an optimum, since new iterations do not improve the mean drag value (see Fig. 5b). In spite of the residual sensitivity existing around the rear edge, any deformation stemming from the current shape sensitivity study implies not only shape modification of the upper wall but also of the lower one in the same sense, which hinders the hypothetical reduction that could be achieved for not having a nil drag sensitivity in Fig. 6(d). This subtlety can be observed in the supplementary movie, where slight oscillations of both walls are observed after the transient period of the optimization process.

Moreover, the influence of selecting a random instant to perform successive optimizations by using the adjoint solver, has been also tested to discard any local influence on the final solution. The consequence is a slower process, that requires a larger number of iterations, until the final shape is converged. Thus, the final optimized geometry can be considered as an overall solution for the optimization process, whose effect on the wake has to be yet deeply investigated. In principle, the mentioned effect of the vortex ring formed upstream of the rear edge may be similar to that created by the extension plates configuration tested by Khalighi et al. (2001), whereby flow reattachment before massive separation leads to a narrower recirculation bubble and an increase of the base pressure, which account for the drag reduction. However, this hypothesis will be further investigated in Section 3.3 performing three-dimensional numerical simulations in more realistic regimes. In that sense, in order to evaluate the performance of the optimized cavity shape at higher Reynolds numbers, we decided to carry out numerical simulations instead of repeating the computational costly optimization procedure, which might be now prone to difficulties and inaccuracies due to the simplifications employed (e.g. frozen turbulence assumption and linearization of adjoint equations). Therefore, to fully understand the flow

Figure 6: Contours of instantaneous drag sensitivity to a localized forcing, $\nabla_f C_d$, (top) and primal axial velocity, u_x , (bottom); along with the corresponding streamlines of the underlying adjoint and primal velocity vectors; for four different steps of the cavity shape optimization process at $Re = 2000$: (a) original shape; (b) intermediate shape #1 (15th iteration in Fig. 5b); (c) intermediate shape #2 (25th iteration in Fig. 5b); and (d) optimal shape.

Figure 7: (a) Time-evolution of the drag coefficient, $C_d(t)$, along with their mean value $\overline{C_d(t)}$ (solid lines), at $Re = 2000$ for four different body geometries: blunt base (model A), straight cavity (model B), intermediate cavity (model C) and optimal cavity (model D). (b) Power spectral density, PSD, in arbitrary units (a.u.), of the drag coefficient fluctuations, $C_d(t)' = C_d(t) - \overline{C_d(t)}$, corresponding to body shapes analyzed in (a). In Fig. 7(b), $St = fh/U_\infty$ has been obtained with the distance between the trailing edges of each body, h .

modifications induced by the optimal shape and how they affect the wake instability and the drag, we compare in the next section the flow characteristic of the original wake with those obtained for the optimized cavity (Fig. 6d), and the intermediate shape #1 (Fig. 6b), which does not present a recirculating flow on the curved wall, for two different Reynolds numbers, i.e. $Re = 2000$ and $Re = 20000$.

3.3. Three-dimensional simulations

In order to corroborate the results previously obtained throughout the optimization process, in the present section the flow characteristics induced by the different configurations are assessed and compared with those obtained with the original body (the body without a base cavity). Thus, four different symmetrical configurations are considered herein, specifically, the body without cavity (model A), the body with a straight cavity (model B), the body with an intermediate cavity which does not present the detachment of the boundary layer at the outer side of the cavity plates at $Re = 2000$ (model C, intermediate shape #1 in Section 3.2), and the final geometry obtained from the shape optimization study (model D), in Section 3.2. The drag coefficient C_d and the characteristic Strouhal numbers, St_{C_d} , as well as the main flow dynamics features, are next presented and described to better understand the effect of adding a cavity of a given shape at the base of the body. To do

<i>Geometry</i>	\overline{C}_d	St_v	R(%)
A	0.819	0.224	–
B	0.778	0.230	5.0
C	0.662	0.227	19.2
D	0.609	0.220	25.6

Table 4: Drag coefficient, vortex shedding Strouhal number and drag reduction obtained from three-dimensional, turbulent simulations at $Re = 2000$, for the four geometries described in the present work.

this, more realistic, accurate three-dimensional unsteady turbulent numerical simulations have been conducted for two Reynolds numbers, namely, $Re = 2000$ and $Re = 20000$, as described in Section 2.3.

3.3.1. Results at $Re = 2000$

The study is first focused on the flow dynamics at $Re = 2000$, which has been originally considered in the optimization study. Thus, Fig. 7(a) shows the temporal evolution of the drag coefficient, $C_d(t)$, for each model at $Re = 2000$. In addition, a thick horizontal line is included representing the mean drag coefficient value, \overline{C}_d , for which a total number of 1600 dimensionless time steps has been considered. It can be observed how the mean drag value decreases monotonically from model A to D, specifically, from $\overline{C}_d \approx 0.819$, for the original body without cavity (model A), to $\overline{C}_d \approx 0.609$, for the optimized geometry (model D), as predicted by the optimization study. In addition, the $C_d(t)$ presents relatively high frequency variations of small amplitude, characteristic of the massive vortex shedding process which takes place at the rear part of the body, and low frequency fluctuations around its mean value, characteristic of the three-dimensional, unstable nature of the flow. Note that the amplitude of the low frequency fluctuations is reduced with the inclusion of the different shape cavities, for which again a monotonic amplitude reduction is observed, i.e. presenting model D the minimum amplitude value. This result indicates that the shape optimization study not only provides with a decrease in the mean drag coefficient, \overline{C}_d , but also induces a stabilizing effect of the body wake, as shown in Fig. 7(b).

Table 4 shows the results of the mean drag, \overline{C}_d , and vortex shedding characteristic Strouhal number, St_v , computed now from the time evolution of axial velocity obtained at a control point, located downstream of the body, in the vicinity of the upper edge of the cavity, specifically at $(x, y, z) = (0.92, 0.5, 0)$. In the computation of the Strouhal number, $St_v = f_v h / U_\infty$, the characteristic height of each cavity geometry has been considered, i.e. the distance between the trailing edges, being $h = 1$ for models A and B, $h = 0.928$ for C and $h = 0.853$ for D. As previously commented, a monotonic mean drag relative reduction, $R(\%) = 100 \times (\overline{C}_{dA} - \overline{C}_{dBCorD}) / \overline{C}_{dA}$, is obtained for each geometry, with a total relative reduction of 25.6% achieved with model D (the optimized body) in this case. This result constitutes a significant drag variation, considering the low mean drag value of the original streamlined body, $\overline{C}_{dA} = 0.819$, and the relatively low Reynolds number, $Re = 2000$, in which the viscous part of the drag coefficient is still important, as reported by Sanmiguel-Rojas et al. (2011). Furthermore, it is worth mentioning that there is a remarkable agreement between the results obtained from the two-dimensional and the three-dimensional analyses.

To better illustrate the effect of including different shape cavities on the flow characteristic frequencies, Fig. 7(b) shows the Power Spectral Density, PSD, corresponding to the drag coefficient fluctuations, $C_d(t)' = C_d(t) - \overline{C}_d(t)$, for the four models. As it has been previously mentioned, two different peaks can be clearly observed. On the one hand, a high frequency peak can be appreciated at $St_{C_d} \simeq 0.45$, which is equal to twice the characteristic vortex shedding frequency obtained from the time evolution of axial velocity on each side of the cavity, $St_{C_d} \simeq 2St_v$, shown in Table 4, since $C_d(t)$ includes the effects of the vortex shedding from the upper and lower sides of the body. On the other hand, a low frequency, more energetic peak is also present, which is characteristic of the three-dimensional, unstable nature of the flow behind the body. In all cases, the inclusion of the subsequent cavities reduces the amplitude of both peaks, being such reduction about 60% when comparing models A and D for the higher St . Therefore, the body with the optimized shape cavity will exhibit a less energetic vortex shedding at the base, as well as a more regularized and

Figure 8: Time-averaged flow field at $z = 0$ and $Re = 2000$: contours of pressure, \bar{p} , and streamlines of the near wake for the different cavity geometries.

less chaotic wake near the body base. In addition, it can also be seen that the peaks become narrower with the inclusion of the different cavities, which indicates the regularization of the flow, as wider peaks are related to three-dimensional disturbances of turbulent wakes, such as vortex dislocations or oblique vortex shedding (Williamson, 1996; Prasad and Williamson, 1997; Parezanović and Cadot, 2012). This amplitude reduction is a consequence of the lower pressure and velocity fluctuations generated in the neighborhood of the body base when a cavity is incorporated, which also provides a less chaotic and narrower wake as it will be shown later. Furthermore, with regard to the vortex shedding at $St_{C_d} \approx 0.45$, characteristic of the massive separation, though St_{C_d} hardly varies with the shape of the cavity added, the same trend is observed for both Re investigated, i.e. it slightly increases from model A to B, whereas decreases monotonically from B to C and subsequently to D. The differences observed in St_{C_d} for the different models are the consequence of two main factors: the modification of the local shear layer at the separation point and the variation of the distance between the upper and lower shear layers. In particular, an increase of the boundary layer thickness reduces the vortex shedding frequency (Gerrard, 1966; Parezanović and Cadot, 2012) while a decrease of the distance between shear layers increases the characteristic frequency, as reported by Molezzi and Dutton (1995). This latter effect could be caused by the stronger interaction between the upper and the lower vortices shed from the body as the distance between both edges decreases. The interaction between both vortices increases the vortex circulation and, consequently, the induced velocities, which make the vortices separate more rapidly. However, it should be noted that, although the vortex emission frequency maybe larger as the distance between the upper and lower shear layer decreases, the resulting Strouhal number can be lower since it has been defined as $St_{C_d} = f_{C_d} h / U_\infty$, and h decreases from model B to D.

To provide with further understanding of the effect of adding the different cavities on the rear part of the body, the mean flow of the near wake is considered next. Thus, Fig. 8 displays the mean near wake flow streamlines together with the corresponding static pressure coefficient contours, \bar{C}_p , within a vertical plane located at half of the domain, i.e. $z = 0$. Apparently, the drag coefficient reduction produced by the shape optimization is motivated by an important decrease of the pressure contribution to the aerodynamic forces. Specifically, note that the base pressure increases significantly with the inclusion of the different cavities. It can be observed how the addition of a straight base cavity (Fig. 8b), not only increases the minimum value

Figure 9: Time sequence of half of a shedding cycle, at $Re = 2000$ and $z = 0$, represented by contours of spanwise vorticity, w_z , for: (a) a body with a straight cavity and (b) a body with the optimized cavity.

Figure 10: Contours of static pressure in the wake ($p = -0.36$), colored by spanwise vorticity: (a) original body without cavity (model A), (b) body with straight cavity (model B), and (c) body with the optimized cavity (model D).

of \overline{C}_p , but also enlarges the dead region nearby the base of the body, displacing downstream the cores of the recirculating flow and thus lengthening it; a phenomenon typically associated to the above-mentioned base pressure increase (Martín-Alcántara et al., 2014). In the case of model C (Fig. 8c), with an improved but not optimized cavity, the new cavity walls deflect towards the wake axis and adopt a shape that reduces the mean shear near the body edge (Molezzi and Dutton, 1995). Such modification in the geometry of the cavity induces a longitudinal adverse pressure gradient which decelerates the flow, and deflects it inwards, generating a recirculating region thinner than in the cases of the body without a cavity and that with a straight cavity. This effect is similar to that produced by the boat-tail device, which basically modifies the rear part of the body making it more streamlined (Choi et al., 2014). Note that, although the recirculation length hardly varies from model B (with a straight cavity) to model C (with an improved non-optimized cavity), there is a consequent shear reduction and an increase of the minimum pressure. Furthermore, in addition to increasing the minimum value of the pressure behind the body, the new cavity displaces the recirculating bubble away from the body, increasing the base pressure and consequently reducing the drag. In the case of model D, i.e. a body with the optimized cavity, the adverse pressure gradient contributes to recover the pressure nearby the body base, making the flow detach at the outer sides of the cavity walls (see Fig. 8d). Since the adverse pressure gradient is greater in the case of model D compared to that of model C, the base pressure increase is larger and, thus, the drag coefficient decreases substantially. The corresponding separated flow over the cavity wall does not contribute significantly to increase \overline{C}_d , but may act as a natural blowing, displacing the low pressure region downstream from the body with the consequent increase in \overline{C}_p .

A close inspection of the temporal evolution of the wake structure also reveals the effects of implementing

Figure 11: (a) Time-evolution of the drag coefficient, $C_d(t)$, along with their mean value $\overline{C_d(t)}$ (solid lines), at $Re = 20000$ for the four body geometries described in this work: blunt base (model A), straight cavity (model B), intermediate cavity (model C) and optimal cavity (model D). (b) Power spectral density, PSD, in arbitrary units (a.u) of the drag coefficient fluctuations, $C_d(t)' = C_d(t) - \overline{C_d(t)}$, corresponding to the different body shapes. In Fig. 11(b), $St = fh/U_\infty$ has been obtained with the distance between the trailing edges of each body, h .

the different types of cavities. In fact, Fig. 9 shows five time sequences of the near field spanwise vorticity contours, for half a vortex shedding period, i.e. $t = t_0$ to $t = t_0 + 1/2 St_v^{-1}$, obtained for models B and D (the bodies with a straight and an optimized cavity, respectively). It is well known that the natural wake that forms behind these kinds of models presents the classical von Kármán vortex street, with an alternating vortex shedding at a characteristic frequency, already identified. It can be observed that, unlike what happens with the optimized cavity, in the case of the straight cavity, the flow remains attached to the body upon reaching the trailing edge. In addition, the flow is nearly parallel to the straight walls in the first case whereas it deflects inwards in the second one. As a consequence, the strength of the vortices shed is significantly lower in the case of the optimized cavity (model D), which results in an increase of the static pressure, as shown in Fig. 8. In this figure, both sequences begin with the formation of a clockwise vortex at the upper plate and the shedding of a counterclockwise vortex at the lower side, which travels downstream, at time $t = t_0$ ($\phi = 0$). In the case of a body a straight cavity (model B), the vortex grows and partly penetrates into the cavity, times $t = t_0 + 1/8 St_v^{-1}$ to $t = t_0 + 3/8 St_v^{-1}$ ($\phi = \pi/4, \pi/2$ and $3\pi/4$) presenting the largest levels of vorticity, i.e. the lowest values of pressure, during these stages. Finally, at time $t = t_0 + 1/2 St_v^{-1}$ ($\phi = \pi$), a counterclockwise vortex starts to form at the trailing edge of the lower plate which grows and eventually displaces the upper vortex downstream. However, in the case of the body with the optimized cavity (model D) the shear layer thickness near the body edge increases, with respect to that of the body with a straight cavity, due to the adverse pressure gradient induced by the curved wall, and the vortex formation process takes place downstream from the body. This, together with the induced inwards velocity component, reduce the spanwise vorticity. Furthermore, note that during the entire shedding cycle, a significantly large *dead* region exists at the rear part of the body, which is the mechanism mainly contributing to the C_d reduction (Viswanath, 1996). The flow dynamics is very similar to that of model B, although in this case there is no spatial coexistence of the two counter-rotating vortices, since they are not confined by the cavity.

Finally, to provide with further evidences of the stabilizing effect of the optimized cavity, the wake flow three-dimensional structures are shown in Fig. 10, which displays static pressure isosurfaces (Park et al., 2006), for $p = -0.36$, colored by the spanwise vorticity, for the original body (model A, Fig. 10a), the one with a straight cavity (model B, Fig. 10b), and the one with the optimized cavity (model D, Fig. 10c). Note that the wake is more chaotic and three-dimensional in the case of model A, resulting in the low frequency energetic peak shown in Fig. 7(b). Furthermore, smaller and more spatially regularized spanwise structures can also be observed when a cavity is added, and especially in the case of model D, inferring the formation of a more slender wake, as it has been previously commented. In this case, the flow becomes more two-dimensional, being

Figure 12: Time-averaged flow field at $z = 0$ and $Re = 20000$: contours of pressure, \bar{p} , and streamlines of the near wake for the different cavity geometries.

the coherent structures shown in Fig. 10(c) almost aligned with the trailing edge, reducing the amplitude of the low frequency fluctuations, as shown in Fig. 7.

3.3.2. Results at $Re = 20000$

The present analysis has been extended to a more realistic, turbulent flow, in order to evaluate the validity and robustness of the optimization study, when different flow conditions are considered. Thus, the same four models described in Section 3.3.1 have been also studied herein at $Re = 20000$. Thus, Fig. 11(a) shows the temporal evolution of the drag coefficient, $C_d(t)$, for each model at $Re = 20000$. It can be inferred from the figure a monotonic reduction of the mean drag, \bar{C}_d , as well as a decrease of the amplitude of both, the low and the high frequency fluctuations (see Fig. 11b), as happens at $Re = 2000$. Note that, the mean drag obtained at this Reynolds number for the body without a cavity, $\bar{C}_d = 0.907$, is larger than that obtained at $Re = 2000$, $\bar{C}_d = 0.819$, (Prasad and Williamson, 1997; Sohankar, 2006; Park et al., 2006). In addition, the viscous contribution to the total drag decreases from 16% at $Re = 2000$ to 8% at $Re = 20000$, thus being the pressure forces responsible for the main contribution to the \bar{C}_d . As a consequence, the potential drag reduction that can be achieved using the optimized shape cavity increases with the Reynolds number (Sanmiguel-Rojas et al., 2011). Indeed, the mean drag value obtained when the optimized cavity is added at the body base decreases from $\bar{C}_d = 0.609$ at $Re = 2000$ to $\bar{C}_d = 0.509$ at $Re = 20000$. The aforementioned results are presented in Table 5, which reports a total drag reduction of 43.9% for model D, a value significantly larger than that obtained with a straight cavity, $R(\%) = 20.3\%$, or with similar devices, such as a multi-cavity (Martín-Alcántara et al., 2014). Although the values of St_v , also included in Table 5, remain almost constant, they follow the same trend observed at $Re = 2000$, i.e. St_v slightly increases from model A to model B, and monotonically decreases from models B to D.

An analysis of the mean flow reveals the effect of the inclusion of the different shape cavities on the rear part of the body. Thus, Fig. 12 shows the mean flow streamlines together with the corresponding static pressure coefficient contours, \bar{C}_p , downstream from the body within the $z = 0$ plane. The flow features are similar to those shown in Fig. 8 at $Re = 2000$, although in this case of larger Re , the boundary layer nearby the trailing

<i>Geometry</i>	\bar{C}_d	St_v	R(%)
A	0.907	0.227	–
B	0.723	0.241	20.3
C	0.630	0.236	30.5
D	0.509	0.232	43.9

Table 5: Drag coefficient, vortex shedding Strouhal number and drag reduction obtained from three-dimensional, turbulent simulations at $Re = 20000$, for the four geometries described in the present work.

Figure 13: Time sequence of half of a shedding cycle, at $Re = 20000$ and $z = 0$, represented by contours of spanwise vorticity, w_z , for: (a) a body with a straight cavity and (b) a body with the optimized cavity.

edge is thinner and the shear stresses are greater than in the case of $Re = 2000$, inducing lower values of the base pressure and a shorter recirculation length for model A as shown in Fig. 12(a). This results are consistent with the increase of the drag coefficient in the case of the body without a cavity reported in Tables 4 and 5. The inclusion of a straight cavity (model B), Fig. 12(b), displaces the recirculation flow downstream from the base of the body, increasing the base pressure and, consequently, reducing the drag coefficient. Furthermore, as happens at $Re = 2000$, the pressure coefficient at the base increases monotonically with models C and D due to the combined effect of the inwards flow deflection and the adverse pressure gradient generated on the outer cavity walls, which makes the flow slow down, increasing the boundary layer and, consequently decreasing shear stresses. However, unlike what happens at $Re = 2000$, the flow does not separate over the concave cavity walls of model D since at $Re = 20000$ the momentum of the flow is sufficiently high to avoid flow separation in the region where the adverse pressure gradient is established. Thus, the flow is no longer ejected downstream from the body and recirculates closer to the base, forming a bubble narrower and shorter than that formed at lower Reynolds numbers because the traverse velocities of the flow at the trailing edge are greater and the growth of the vortices shed is now limited by the cavity. Consequently, in this particular case, the optimized cavity behaved as a tilted rear edge, but with the additional effect of including a cavity.

Figure 13 shows five time sequences of the spanwise vorticity contours at the central vertical plane, again for half the corresponding vortex shedding period (from $t = t_0$ to $t = t_0 + 1/2 St_v^{-1}$), for the body with a straight cavity (model B) and that with the optimized one (model D). The sequence displays the vortex formation, growth and shedding from the upper wall in both cases. It can be observed in Fig. 13(a) that the high level of turbulence in the boundary layer produces the vortex fragmentation in the case of the straight cavity (Molezzi and Dutton, 1995; Prasad and Williamson, 1997). Furthermore, in this case the forming vortex penetrates inside the cavity entirely almost from the initial stages and grows, while it remains confined within the cavity

Figure 14: Time-averaged drag coefficient obtained for the four different body geometries described in this work at $Re = 2000$ (\bullet) and $Re = 20000$ (\blacktriangle) respectively.

plates, until a counter-rotating vortex starts to form at the lower wall. Notice that, the upper, forming vortex tears a piece of a vortex previously shed from the lower wall and pushes it inside the cavity. Although not shown in Fig. 13, the same sequence takes place when a vortex begins to form at the lower edge, tearing a portion of the vortex shed from the upper wall. This fact, explains that the mean flow does not exhibit a clear and significant *dead flow* region at the base cavity (see Fig. 12b). However, in the case of model D, the upper and lower vortices interact but do not penetrate inside the cavity, displacing the lowest pressure region downstream from the body base. Finally, the stabilization and regularization effect of the optimized cavity can be also inferred from the vortex fragmentation suppression, which indicates that both the level of turbulence and the oscillations amplitude are significantly reduced in this case.

To summarize, Fig. 14 shows the mean drag values, \bar{C}_d , obtained at $Re = 2000$ and $Re = 20000$ with the four models considered here. It is evident the drag reduction achieved when the geometry of the cavity is conveniently designed applying the shape optimization procedure described in Section 3.2, which not only reduces the \bar{C}_d at the Re of study, but which turns out to be also very effective under different flow conditions. Therefore, this mathematically supported technique improves significantly the devices proposed, based on the flow dynamics knowledge and experience, and constitutes a powerful, useful tool to be applied in this field.

4. Conclusions

The present work evaluates the efficiency of different mechanisms proposed to reduce the drag coefficient of two-dimensional bluff bodies with rear cavities, whose performance as control device is known to be limited by its depth, using the adjoint-based sensitivity formulation. Considering the flow and the body shape sensitivity of the drag to a localized forcing, two passive control techniques, consisting in wake modifications by means of the placement of small control cylinders in the near wake and structure topological modifications, have been evaluated to achieve additional drag reduction with rear cavities. Therefore, sensitivity computations have been carried out following the simplified adjoint-based linear steady analysis developed by Meliga et al. (2014) for unsteady flows, for which the drag sensitivity to localized forcing, $\nabla_f \bar{C}_d$, corresponds to the mean linear adjoint velocity $\bar{\mathbf{u}}^\dagger$. This approach has been proven to properly retrieve the main features regarding the most sensitive regions around the bluff body and the drag reduction values. Section 3.1 includes the validation

analysis in the case of a square cylinder, and drag sensitivity maps for the bluff body with a straight cavity at $Re = 2000$. It was shown (Fig. 3) that the mean drag sensitivity is highest at the rear edges of the straight cavity, where control cylinders should be placed in order to achieve largest drag reduction. A first order prediction of such mean drag decrease is given by Eq. (11) (Fig. 3b), which gives negligible values of the drag reduction when control cylinders are placed in an optimal location $(x_c, y_c) = (0.368, \pm 0.428)$. A deeper analysis on the effect of such configuration on drag and wake properties is performed by means of unsteady RANS simulations. The results show that control cylinders placed in zones of highest sensitivity lead to drag reduction and wake stabilization, by altering the shedding process, as detailed in Parezanović and Cadot (2012). The flow reattaches around each cylinder, reducing the entrainment into the recirculation region, whose length increases, and subsequently the base pressure also increases, what accounts for the drag reduction. Besides, the axial velocity gradient is weakened and the backflow is also hindered, giving rise to an overall wake stabilization observed through reduction of drag fluctuations amplitude, $C_d(t)'$, of approximately 47% (Fig. 4). However, the mean drag reduction is very small, i.e. 0.6%, suggesting that a more efficient control alternative must be sought.

A second control strategy based on cavity shape modifications has been analyzed at $Re = 2000$, as a way to overcome the limitations in the drag reduction imposed by fixed cavity depths. After obtaining the drag sensitivity to flow modifications in Section 3.1, the drag shape sensitivity on the body surface was computed using Eq. (10). This variable has been used to guide local structure deformations within a defined control box, obtaining progressive drag reductions by means of an iterative one-shot optimization process, that combines the use of the former adjoint-based sensitivity solver and a free-form deformation CFD toolbox. An instantaneous approach has been employed, whereby we have selected instants of alternate highest sensitivity near the cavity, i.e. vortex shedding events in each cavity side. It has been demonstrated that this strategy helps to design cavity geometries that reduces the drag coefficient of the body, reaching an *optimal* shape after a few iterations, for which an asymptotic drag reduction of approximately 23% is obtained, as Fig. 5 shows. At this point, new local modifications do not improve the mean drag since the sensitivity is barely residual (Fig. 6). The optimized shape consists of a curved wall, that promotes local recirculation and an inwards deflection of the flow before massive separation, what leads to a narrower recirculation bubble and an increase of the base pressure.

To deeply explore the physical mechanisms behind the optimized shape that fosters the observed drag reduction, we have performed unsteady three-dimensional IDDES numerical simulations at two different Reynolds numbers, $Re = 2000$ and 20000 respectively. The numerical computations corroborate the results obtained by the drag sensitivity analysis, showing that the drag is monotonically reduced as the cavity walls are conveniently curved. At $Re = 2000$, the optimized shape cavity provides a 25.6% drag reduction, relative to that of the original body, i.e. without cavity, Fig. 7(a) and Table 4. This reduction is achieved by the combination of an induced inwards flow deflection, which replicates a slanted rear surface, together with the base cavity effect, and a flow deceleration caused by the generation of an adverse pressure gradient near the trailing edge of the body. The curved cavity displaces the recirculation bubble downstream of the body, increasing the mean base pressure coefficient \bar{C}_p (Fig. 8), similar to what happens when base bleed is used as control mechanism (Sanmiguel-Rojas et al., 2009). Furthermore, the addition of an optimized cavity significantly reduces the energy of the flow and the strength of the vortical structures of wake in the near field (Figs. 7b and 9). Consequently, the flow is also regularized and a narrower, more slender and less chaotic wake forms (Figs. 9 and 10). Although the optimal shape has been obtained for $Re = 2000$, it is also very efficient at $Re = 20000$, demonstrating that the procedure is robust. In fact, the drag reduction achieved at $Re = 20000$ is even larger than that obtained at $Re = 2000$, due to the higher adverse pressure gradient before separation and the decrease of the viscous contribution to the drag coefficient. Altogether, adding an optimized cavity provided a total mean drag reduction of 43.9% (Table 5), and reduced the amplitude of the velocity fluctuations generated behind the body (see Figs. 11(b) and 13). Consequently, it has been corroborated that the use of adjoint methods, linked to shape optimization, are efficient tools for the control of flow around bluff bodies, improving the aerodynamic performance of drag reduction devices.

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